

Visual Human Factor Issues Related to Virtual Reality Devices and Interfaces

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Abstract: Newer technological breakthroughs come with their own set of risks. The same may be said for Virtual Reality Devices utilized in virtual reality environments. The current study focuses on various human factors related issues (bodily discomforts), immersiveness in relation to Virtual Reality Devices (Cardboard devices, Open devices, Closed devices), duration, and different VR Interfaces. A between-group study was conducted on 90 users who were provided with three different types of virtual reality devices and three distinct game interfaces to play on each device. The findings from this study's statistical data will aid in the development of improved VR devices in the near future. It will also help to reduce the current human factors-related issues associated with VR devices as well as throw light on the immersiveness due to type of devices and duration of usage of VR devices.

Practical Implications: This paper unfolds VR related eye sicknesses and interface design related issues causing eye sicknesses. A human factors guideline can be developed based on findings of the current study. The VR game interfaces can be evaluated using similar study protocol.

Keywords: Degree of Artificiality; Game; Head-Mounted Display; Human Factors; Virtual Reality; VR Interfaces

1. Introduction and Background of Research

Over the last two decades, the growth of virtual reality (VR) tools has enhanced their application in experimental psychological settings. The VR is convincing to researchers because of the nearly endless possibilities for creating stimuli. As a result, it has expanded to fields such as clinical and developmental psychology, which one might not have expected initially (Wilson and Soranzo 2015). In addition to the numerous benefits of using virtual reality, there are also many disadvantages and unanswered questions.

This paper will focus on the eye related issues (redness of eye, wetness of eye), presence and degree of artificiality in relation with the VR devices, duration and various VR Interfaces.

2. Literature Review

Virtual Reality is a branch of computing that aims to create a virtual world, immerse oneself in it, and allow one to interact with this world while employing specific devices to simulate an environment and excite one with input to make the experience as realistic as possible (Boas 2013).

As virtual reality promises to make interaction as real as possible, The VR devices and VR systems have applications in Medical Training Program (Gallagher et al. 2005), Fear/Panic Reduction (Rothbaum et al. 2000), Rehabilitation (Sapostnik et al. 2010), Maintenance Manual Creation (De Sa and Zachmann 1999), Gaming (Rendon et al. 2012) etc. However, human factors related problems such as Presence, Simulation Sickness, and cyber-sickness are also reported in the literature

Email Corresponding Author: chowdhuryanirban14@gmail.com | Vol. 1 Issue 1 pp. 1-7.

Cite as - Aher, M., Multanwala, H., Goswami, M. & Chowdhury, A. (2022). Visual Human Factor Issues Related to Virtual Reality Devices and Interfaces. *International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences*, 1 (1), 1-7.

(Biocca 1992; Davis, Nesbitt, and Nalivaiko, 2015). It is reported in the literature that there are many problems prevalent in case of VDT usage. These problems are eye irritation, headache, redness of the eye, dryness of the eye (Thomson 1998; Tsubota and Nakamori 1993), neck pain (Bergqvist et al. 1995), low back pain (Bergqvist et al. 1995; Hales et al. 1994), nausea (Biocca 1992), vomit feeling (Biocca 1992), motion sickness (Biocca 1992), presence (Biocca 1992), etc. These problems are also time-dependent. If time is increased the prevalence of these problems is more. Therefore, there is a chance of prevalence of these human factors related problems in case of VR devices.

At present, there are multiple VR Devices in the market; for instances, Facebook purchased Oculus VR (which was developed by Palmer Luckey, and funded via Kickstarter for \$2 billion), Microsoft's HoloLens, HTC's Vive VR, Sony PlayStation VR, Google's Daydream VR headset. In addition, many other technology giants have entered this emerging sector with their headsets. But the question remains - are there any eye related symptoms faced such as eye irritation, dryness of the eyes, redness of the eyes, wetness of the eyes? Are there any presence and degree of artificiality related issues due to the usage of different VR Devices?

2.1. *Virtual Reality Interfaces*

The Virtual Reality Interface plays an important role in making the user feel immersed in the environment created therefore contributing towards the Degree of presence and degree of artificiality factor.

Although virtual reality has found success in specific applications and industries, it has yet to acquire widespread acceptance as a means of communicating with our computers. The obstacles that have plagued VR technology range from extremely limiting and cumbersome interfaces to a lack of applications that can take advantage of the medium (Powell, R. R. 2007). In current scenario, human factors oriented issues limit the duration of use of this medium.

The primary challenge in the virtual reality field is that to construct the ideal virtual reality system, one must concentrate on the interface between man and the machine. The interface is the application in virtual reality. It is the interface that permits a man to become immersed in a world that has been built artificially. It's the interface that enables him to communicate with his artificial environment. The interface is what determines the virtual environment's limitations.

3. Hypothesis

3.1. *Null Hypothesis 1*

There is no significant relationship between Duration of VR Device usage and Wetness of the eyes.

3.2. *Null Hypothesis 2*

There is no significant difference in redness of the eye experienced due to various VR Devices Usage (Open Advanced, Closed Advanced and Basic Cardboard) and VR Games (Interfaces)

3.3. *Null Hypothesis 3*

There is no significant difference in degree of artificiality due to various VR Devices Usage (Open Advanced, Closed Advanced and Basic Cardboard) and VR Games (Interfaces)

Figure 1. The VR Devices used in the experiment.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 *Participant and Sampling*

A total of 90 participants took part in the research chosen through simple random sampling. For the following research, we have included basic VR devices, sitting position and standing position, open and closed devices, advanced devices, iOS /

android compatible devices, ergonomics of devices. The age group ranges from 15 to 30 years, and users aged above 30yrs were excluded in this study. The devices those are compatible only with Microsoft and other operating systems were in current study.

5. Tools and Apparatus used

5.1 VR Devices Used in Experiment

The participants were divided into 3 groups of 30 each. Each group of 30 participants were tested with one of the VR Devices i.e. Open, Closed and Cardboard devices (see [Figure 1](#)). 3 games were selected i.e. VR Subway Run, InCell VR and Maze VR.

Table 1. Specification for Virtual Reality Devices.

Device Type	Cardboard Device	Open Device	Closed Device
Device Name	Get Cardboard DIY Virtual Reality Kit (VR headset glasses) Inspired from Google Cardboard	Ant VR	JT VR BOX 2.0 Virtual Reality Glasses, 2016 3D VR Headsets
Weight	127 g	159 g	422 g
Product Dimensions	25.4 x 13.5 x 2.1 cm	16 x 6.1 x 10.4 cm	13.5 x 19.5 x 11 cm
Padding	Without Padding	With Padding	With Padding
Spectacle	Cannot use Spectacle	Can use Spectacle	Can use Spectacle

Table 2. Virtual Reality Interfaces.

Device Name	Redmi 3s Used with Cardboard VR Device	Yotaphone 2 Used with Open VR Device	i-Phone 6s Used with Closed VR Device
Product Dimensions	139.3 x 69.6 x 8.5 mm (5.48 x 2.74 x 0.33 in)	144.9 x 69.4 x 9 mm (5.70 x 2.73 x 0.35 in)	138.3 x 67.1 x 7.1 mm (5.44 x 2.64 x 0.28 in)
Weight	144 g	145 g	143 g
Type	IPS LCD capacitive touchscreen, 16M colors	AMOLED capacitive touchscreen, 16M colors	LED-backlit IPS LCD, capacitive touchscreen, 16M colors
Size	5.0 inches, 68.9 cm ² (~71.1% screen-to-body ratio)	5.0 inches, 68.6 cm ² (~68.2% screen-to-body ratio)	4.7 inches, 60.9 cm ² (~65.6% screen-to-body ratio)
Screen to body Ratio	71.1%	68.2%	65.6%
Resolution	720 x 1280 pixels,	1080 x 1920 pixels	750 x 1334 pixels
Ratio	16:9	16:9	16:9
Density	294 ppi	442 ppi	326
OS	Android 6.0.1 (Marshmallow)	Android 4.4.3 (KitKat), upgradable to 6.0 (Marshmallow)	iOS 9, upgradable to iOS 11.0.2

Chipset	Qualcomm MSM8937 Snapdragon 430	Qualcomm Snapdragon 801	Apple A9
CPU	Octa-core 1.4 GHz Cortex-A53	Quad-core 2.3 GHz Krait 400	Dual-core 1.84 GHz Twister
GPU	Adreno 505	Adreno 330	PowerVR GT7600 (six-core graphics)

5.2 Questionnaire

Questionnaire was designed to gather data about the user's perceptions about degree of artificiality of game interface and human factor related issues after playing the game. The questions were based on the 10 Points facial pain rating scale which is a modified version of the Wong Baker Scale (Wong and Baker 2001).

6. Research Procedure

The participants were divided into 3 groups of 30 each. Each group of 30 participants were tested with one of the VR Devices i.e. Open, Closed and Cardboard devices. Three games were selected i.e. VR Subway Run, InCell VR and Maze VR. It was ensured that the games were available on both the platforms used for the procedure i.e. Android and iOS. Ten out of the 30 users belonging to one group of the VR Device were made to play one of the games selected.

Table 3. Between groups experimental method.

<i>Independent variable = VR Device / Time = 5 minutes vs more than 5 minutes</i>		
Device 1	Device 2	Device 3
Basic Cardboard VR device	Open VR device	Closed VR device
Group A 30	Group B 30	Group C 30
<i>Dependent Variables</i>		
Eye related issues (eye irritation, dryness of the eyes, redness of the eyes, wetness of the eyes), and degree of artificiality	Eye related issues (eye irritation, dryness of the eyes, redness of the eyes, wetness of the eyes) and degree of artificiality	Eye related issues (eye irritation, dryness of the eyes, redness of the eyes, wetness of the eyes), and degree of artificiality

7. Results and Discussion

7.1 Redness of the eye with respect to Devices

For Cardboard Device, mean value for redness of the eye when used for 5 minutes is 1.36 ± 2.11 (Mean \pm S.D.) whereas the mean value for Open Device is 0.43 ± 1.20 and for closed device it is 1.3 ± 1.64 which shows that redness of the eye for Cardboard Device is higher than it is for Open and Closed Device: whereas, redness of the eye observed in Open device was comparatively less than other devices (see [Figure 2](#)).

Figure 2. Redness of the eye experienced in different devices.

Table 4. Mean values and significance level of redness of the eye in different devices.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Wetness of the eye	Between Groups	16.26	2	8.13	3.79	0.026

In order to test the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between redness of the eye and device used, a between group ANOVA was performed.

The independent between-groups ANOVA yielded significance effect [$F(2, 87) = 3.79, p = .026$] (see [Table 4](#)). Thus, the null hypothesis of there is no difference between the redness of the eye and different devices used was rejected.

7.2 Wetness of the eye (after 5 Minutes) with respect to devices

For Cardboard device, mean value for wetness of the eye when used more than 5 minutes is 1.87 ± 2.01 ($M \pm SD$) whereas the mean value for Open device is 0.97 ± 1.90 and for closed device it is 0.57 ± 1.45 which shows that wetness of the eye for Cardboard device is higher than it is for Open and Closed device; whereas, wetness of the eye observed in closed device was comparatively less than other devices (see [Figure 3](#)).

Figure 3. Wetness of the eye experienced in different devices.

Table 5. Mean Values and significance level of wetness of the eye in different devices.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Wetness of the eye	Between Groups	26.60	2	13.30	4.07	.020

When between group ANOVA (see [Table 5](#)) was performed in order to test the hypothesis, no significant relation was found between the wetness of the eye and different devices used

7.3 Degree of Artificiality with respect to Game Interfaces

In order to test the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between game interfaces and degree of artificiality, a between group ANOVA was performed.

Table 6. Mean Values and significance level of artificiality in different game interfaces.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Degree of Artificiality	Between Groups	81.622	2	12.712	6.934	.002

The independent between-groups ANOVA yielded significance effect [$F(2, 87) = 6.93, p=.002$] (See [Table 6](#)). Thus, the null hypothesis of no difference between the degree of artificiality and the different game interfaces was rejected.

8. Conclusion

The present study indicated that various VR devices might cause several eye-related concerns (eye irritation, dryness of eyes, wetness of eyes, and degree of artificiality). In addition, the duration of VR device usage plays a role to increase all the above-mentioned issues. The main findings from the study suggest that there are certain eye issues (redness of the eye, wetness of the eye) associated with virtual interface, duration, and different VR device types (like cardboard, open, and closed devices). There are possibilities of wetness of eyes if VR game players are playing games for more than 5 minutes using Google cardboard device; whereas, eye redness is generally less when gamers are playing VR games using Open device. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the duration of the game played and device type play a significant role in the end-user experience and should be considered when creating future VR devices and interfaces.

Virtual reality and associated technologies would enable more cost-effective training, enhanced situational awareness, and data visualization. However, there are human factors related challenges, a designer or an ergonomist need to overcome in near future. Many breakthroughs in VR interface technology have been made by utilizing the limitations of human senses such as generating motion video at 30 frames per second to approximate reality. To gain a better understanding of the senses' inherent functions, it would be better to exploit their limits and eliminate the negative impacts that they currently have on the eyes, as evidenced by the current research.

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